

Enhancing drug delivery through chemical modification of chitosan: A review

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Abstract

Chitosan is a natural polysaccharide used in the pharmaceutical industry and medicine due to its hydrophilic, biocompatible, biodegradable, and non-toxic properties. However, it is insoluble in water, which limits its applications. Therefore, various chemical modifications of chitosan have been developed, offering improved biocompatibility, bioactivity, biodegradability, and non-toxicity while retaining its pharmacological effects. Chitosan has various derivatives, including carboxymethylated, acylated, quaternary ammonium, and thiolated forms. In addition to improving the physical and chemical properties of chitosan, these derivatives are also used as drug delivery systems. Studies have been conducted on the immobilization of drugs such as selegiline, doxorubicin, and tobramycin to modify chitosan. This review aims to highlight the advantages of chemical modification of chitosan and to encourage further research in this still vast area, as chemically modified chitosans have shown promising potential for application in various fields of medicine, pharmacy, and industry.

Keywords

chemically modified chitosan, controlled release, drug delivery applications, glycosylated chitosan, mucoadhesive polymers

Introduction

Chitosan, as displayed in Fig. 1, is a natural polysaccharide used in the pharmaceutical industry and medicine for its hydrophilic, biocompatible, biodegradable, and non-toxic properties. It is a linear polymer consisting of N-acetyl-D-glucosamine and D-glucosamine units, randomly repeated and linked by $\alpha(1\rightarrow4)$ glycosidic bonds (Fig. 1). Chitosan accelerates wound healing, has antacid, antibacterial, and antitumor effects, and absorbs toxic metals (mercury, lead, and cadmium) (Guadarrama-Escobar et al. 2023; Sangnim et al. 2023).

Figure 1. Structure of chitosan.

Chitosan is not very common in nature and is mainly obtained by deacetylation of chitin, its source polymer. Chitin is the second most abundant polysaccharide on

Earth, preceded only by cellulose. It is found in the cell walls of green algae and fungi, the cuticles of insects and arachnids, and the exoskeletons of crustaceans (de Queiroz Antonino et al. 2017). However, chitosan is insoluble in water and most organic solvents; therefore, its applications in various fields are constrained. Chitosan derivatives can be obtained by the chemical modification of its functional groups. In the chitosan molecule, hydroxyl and amino groups are prone to chemical reactions. Chemical modification can not only improve the physical and chemical properties of chitosan but also preserve its unique properties and expand the scope of application of its derivatives. Modified chitosan exhibits enhanced biocompatibility, bioactivity, biodegradability, and non-toxicity while retaining its bactericidal, antibacterial, anticancer, and antiviral pharmacological effects (Wang et al. 2020).

The importance of chitosan and its derivatives for scientific development is also evident in forecasts indicating that the global chitosan market will reach approximately \$91.99 billion by 2033, with an expected growth rate of 22.31% due to the widespread use of chitosan in industry (Chitosan Market Size Projected to Reach USD 101.06 Bn 2024).

In this review, we have explored how various chemical modifications of chitosan, such as thiolation, quaternization, carboxymethylation, and hydrophobic grafting, enhance its effectiveness for drug delivery across different administration routes, including oral, injectable, mucosal, and transdermal. Understanding how these improvements are accomplished requires examining the strategies available for the chemical modification of chitosan and the functional groups involved.

Types of chitosan modifications

Chitosan has three reactive functional groups: an amino group (-NH₂) located at C2-NH₂ and two hydroxyl groups located at C3-OH and C6-OH. The C6-OH hydroxyl

group is more chemically active than that at C3-OH. Using appropriate reagents, the amino group of chitosan can be chemically modified to yield N-modified derivatives. In contrast, modification of the hydroxyl groups results in O-modified derivatives, thereby providing improved physicochemical properties. Chemical modification of chitosan can be achieved through any of its functional groups. However, derivatives obtained through reactions with its hydroxyl groups result in the smallest changes in its biophysical properties (Jha and Mayanovic 2023). Chitosan can be combined with natural (gelatin, hyaluronic acid, collagen, silk, alginate, starch, cellulose) and synthetic (polyvinyl alcohol (PVA), polyethylene oxide (PEO), polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP), poly(N-isopropylacrylamide) (PNIPAm), polycaprolactone (PCL), polylactic acid (PLA), poly(L-lactic acid) (PLLA), polyacrylic acid (PAA)) polymers, as well as with other promising materials such as aloe vera, silicon dioxide, and many others, which enables the creation of multifunctional, tunable biomaterials that simultaneously achieve mechanical robustness, controlled degradation, and superior biological performance, making them highly suitable for tissue engineering, wound healing, drug delivery, and implantable medical devices. Chitosan can be chemically modified through thiolation, quaternization, carboxylation, or acylation, resulting in derivatives with altered charge, solubility, and reactive properties. These functional groups expand the polymer's applicability in drug delivery, mucoadhesive systems, and biomedical formulations, as shown in Fig. 2 (Kołodziejska et al. 2021).

Based on these reactive sites and modification routes, several distinct classes of chitosan derivatives have been developed, among which thiolated chitosan is one of the most extensively studied.

Thiolated chitosan

Chemical modifications of chitosan have been developed using a variety of mercapto carboxylic acids, including

Figure 2. A range of chemically modified chitosan derivatives has been developed, including carboxymethylated, acylated, quaternary ammonium, and thiolated forms (created with BioRender; accessed February 2025).

mercaptopropionic acid, 2-methyl-3-sulfanilpropanoic acid, mercaptohexanoic acid, and mercaptooctanoic acid, by various research teams. In addition to being carriers for medicinal substances, these chitosan derivatives also exhibit significant antibacterial properties (Croce et al. 2016). One of the risks in the preparation of thiolated chitosans is oxidation of the sulfhydryl group. This can be prevented by adding 2-mercaptoethanol, depending on the method of preparation of the derivative, or by carrying out the reaction at an acidic pH below 5 (Tekade et al. 2019). Chitosan has demonstrated enhanced penetration of drugs through the mucosa of the intestine, nose, mouth, and vagina (Ways et al. 2018). While the mucoadhesion of unmodified chitosan primarily relies on non-covalent interactions, thiolated chitosan derivatives possess free thiol groups that enable the formation of covalent disulfide bonds with cysteine-rich subdomains of mucin glycoproteins (Federer et al. 2021). Thiolated chitosan demonstrates several advantages, including a 6- to 100-fold improvement in mucoadhesion, a 1.6- to 3-fold increase in permeability, and *in situ* gelling properties at physiological pH. Together, these properties improve drug residence time and increase bioavailability (Dalvin 2022). Thiolated polymers oxidize at physiological pH, leading to the formation of cross-links between their chains. In the pH range of 5 to 6, they form both intramolecular and intermolecular disulfide bonds, creating a three-dimensional gel network. This structure improves the stability of the delivery system and maintains a sustained, controlled release of the drug. Thus, thiolated chitosans are suitable for application to various mucosal tissues, including the nasal, oral, ocular, and vaginal surfaces (Eker Fidan et al. 2025). Furthermore, Hintzen et al. demonstrated that the molecular weight of thiolated chitosan influences its *in situ* gelation behavior. Derivatives with lower molecular weight showed a marked increase in viscosity because their polymer chains are more flexible and mobile, allowing a greater extent of cross-linking (Hintzen et al. 2012). As the concentration of hydroxide ions increases, more negatively charged thiolate anions become available, which enhances the formation of disulfide bonds. Therefore, thiolated chitosans such as chitosan-thioglycolic acid do not form disulfide bonds at pH levels below 5, making them unsuitable as *in situ* gelling systems for drug delivery at application sites with an acidic pH (Federer et al. 2021).

In another study, a modification of chitosan with thioglycolic acid was developed, which was used both independently and as a drug carrier for obesity therapy. The cytotoxicity of that derivative was evaluated by the WST-1 cell viability assay and live/dead staining. Both tests showed that thiolated chitosan had negligible cytotoxicity and desirable biocompatibility. Further studies demonstrated that thiolated chitosan had superior mucoadhesive properties compared to chitosan itself (Tzu-Chien Chen et al. 2021). Attempts have been made to further pegylate thiolated chitosan. The synthesized derivatives exhibited good solubility in water and better mucoadhesion than chitosan but did not differ significantly from the mucoad-

hesive properties of pure thiolated chitosan (Hauptstein et al. 2014).

In addition to thiolation, several other chemical modification strategies have been explored to tailor chitosan functionality, among which sulfation represents a distinct and biologically active approach.

Sulfated chitosan

Sulfated chitosan derivatives have also been developed for use in medicine and pharmacy. However, their properties depend strongly on the specific conditions of sulfation. The type of sulfating reagent, solvent system, reaction temperature, and reaction duration are crucial in determining the properties of the final product. Harsh reagents (e.g., sulfuric acid, oleum, chlorosulfonic acid, sulfur trioxide) can cause significant polymer degradation, whereas their use with Lewis bases minimizes this effect. Different reaction media lead to heterogeneous, homogeneous, or pseudo-homogeneous sulfation, producing structurally distinct derivatives even from the same starting material. These variations determine the physicochemical and biological properties of the resulting products, ultimately affecting their suitability for biomedical applications. In the context of drug delivery, such variations directly influence molecular weight, degree of substitution, charge distribution, and solubility, thereby governing drug loading capacity, carrier stability, and release behavior. Controlled sulfation improves aqueous solubility and enables favorable electrostatic interactions with therapeutic agents, while excessive degradation compromises structural integrity. Consequently, precise control of sulfation conditions is essential for tailoring chitosan-based carriers with optimized drug delivery performance (Dimassi et al. 2018). Bolshakov et al. (2025) conducted a series of tests on laboratory animals to assess the possibility of reducing atherosclerotic plaques in the blood vessels of the lower limbs in rabbits. They found that sulfated chitosan, in contact with blood, binds to high- and low-density lipoproteins. This binding, in turn, leads to a decrease in the plasma atherogenic coefficient. The study displays the great potential of sulfated chitosans for the local treatment of atherosclerosis. Sulfated chitosan and oligochitosan with a molecular weight of 1,277–100 kDa, a 0–25% degree of acetylation, and a 0.82–1.55 degree of sulfate substitution exhibit antiviral activity against human papillomavirus, HIV-1, vesicular stomatitis virus, and Newcastle disease virus (NDV). The sulfation of chitosan is important for the effective and selective inhibition of HIV and other enveloped viruses. The antiviral activity of sulfated chitosan and sulfated chitin is influenced by the site of sulfation, while that of sulfated chitosan is also enhanced by a higher degree of sulfation (Karthik et al. 2016). Nishimura et al. proposed that sulfate groups located at the O-3 and O-2 positions of chitin sulfates can specifically bind to the HIV-1 gp120 protein, whereas sulfation at the O-6 position may predominantly enhance anticoagulant activity through nonspecific ionic interactions with thrombin or other coagulation factors (Nishimura et al. 1998). Chi-

tosan derivatives with a higher sulfate content and higher molecular weight (100 kDa) show greater antiviral activity than those with a lower molecular weight (25 kDa) (Stepanov et al. 2012; Tan et al. 2022).

Another relevant modification strategy is chitosan phosphorylation, which introduces negatively charged functional groups with unique biological implications.

Phosphorylated chitosan

Phosphorylated chitosan derivatives have garnered attention due to their characteristics, including high water solubility and a tendency to chelate metals. The water solubility of phosphorylated chitosan is inversely proportional to its degree of substitution (DS) and degree of deacetylation. Modified chitosan with high DS is insoluble in water due to its amphoteric properties, as the phosphate groups introduced into the chitosan structure promote inter- and intramolecular cross-linking (Bombaldi de Souza et al. 2020). These types of biopolymers have important applications in tissue regeneration, as intermediates in drug manufacturing, and in the food industry (Jayakumar et al. 2006). Phosphorylated chitin and chitosan can be synthesized through several efficient methods involving different phosphorylating systems. Common approaches include reactions with P_2O_5 in methanesulphonic acid, orthophosphoric acid/urea in DMF, grafting with phosphate-containing monomers, or incorporation of methylene phosphonic groups via the Moedritzer–Irani reaction. Other strategies use alkaline chitosan with chlorophosphate reagents, 1-ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl) carbodiimide (EDC)-mediated graft copolymerization, or mixed $H_3PO_4/Et_3PO_4/P_2O_5$ systems, each enabling control over the degree of substitution and specific functional group introduction. Overall, these methods produce phosphorylated derivatives with improved solubility, catalytic reactivity, and enhanced biological properties such as antimicrobial activity (Jayakumar et al. 2008). Additionally, phosphorylated chitosan is synthesized by reacting chitosan with orthophosphoric acid at 150 °C in the presence of urea as a catalyst and dimethylformamide (DMF) as a solvent (Negm et al. 2020). Phosphorylated chitosans can find various applications in medicine and pharmacy. By incorporating phosphocreatine into chitosan molecular chains under mild conditions, Liu et al. synthesized phosphorylated chitosan hydrogels, which could not only promote alkaline phosphatase activity and mineralization but also upregulate the expression of osteogenic-related genes and proteins. The hydrogels were fabricated by UV-initiated polymerization of methacrylamide chitosan and phosphocreatine-modified methacrylamide chitosan, producing materials with graded phosphocreatine content. Although phosphocreatine incorporation did not alter the hydrogel morphology or pore architecture, the presence of phosphate groups significantly enhanced functional properties. The increase in phosphocreatine content led to greater hydrophilicity (reflected in faster swelling), high-

er protein adsorption, and accelerated mineralization, demonstrating that the phosphate-bearing substituents directly modulate bioactivity while leaving the structural framework intact (Liu et al. 2020). Anushree and her team investigated the effects of phosphorylated chitosan on diabetic wound healing. Compared with unmodified chitosan, the synthesized phosphorylated derivative demonstrated a higher reducing capacity and markedly enhanced metal-chelating activity. Notably, the improvement in chelation was most pronounced at lower concentrations, with the relative advantage gradually decreasing as the concentration increased. Unlike untreated wounds, wounds treated with water-soluble phosphorylated chitosan showed a 30% higher rate of contraction. Wounds treated with phosphorylated chitosan showed an increased number of fibroblasts, a thicker epithelial layer, and improved collagen deposition (Anushree et al. 2023). Another study showed the effects of phosphorylated chitosan on slowing dentin erosion. The experiment conducted by Beltrame et al. demonstrated a 33% reduction in dentin erosion when phosphorylated chitosan was applied. However, the team noted that further toxicity testing was needed to provide accurate data on the benefits of using phosphorylated chitosan for this purpose (Beltrame et al. 2018). The possible use of phosphorylated chitosan as a drug delivery system for intramuscular administration of vaccines is also of interest. Wei et al. used phosphorylated chitosan (PCS) with a degree of substitution of 18.4%, which is water-soluble at pH 7 but begins to gel at pH above 7. The water-soluble and pH-sensitive nature of PCS suggests its potential as a gentle and convenient vaccine delivery platform, offering advantages over traditional chitosan-based systems. Neutral aqueous solutions of phosphorylated chitosan containing ovalbumin antigen (PCS/OVA) were injected intramuscularly into laboratory mice, resulting in the transformation of the solution into a gel. The results showed a significant increase in antigen-specific immune response levels, with the 30 mg/mL PCS/OVA formulation consistently demonstrating superior immunization efficacy. It is assumed that the enhanced effect of immunization is due to the ability of the phosphorylated chitosan-based hydrogel to release the antigen in a controlled manner, which opens up additional prospects for vaccine development (Wei et al. 2017).

In contrast to phosphorylated derivatives, quaternary ammonium chitosans represent a distinct class of modified chitosans characterized by permanently cationic functionality.

Quaternary ammonium chitosan

Quaternization of chitosan with quaternary ammonium groups or small molecules of quaternary ammonium salts at C6–OH or C2–NH₂ produces chitosan derivatives with enhanced solubility and antimicrobial properties, which favors their use in various fields (El-Araby et al. 2023). These materials are considered highly promising owing to their ready availability, affordability, biocompatibility,

biodegradability, and adjustable properties through targeted chemical modifications. Quaternization of chitosan enhances its antibacterial action due to the increased electrostatic interaction between the positively charged quaternary ammonium ion and the negatively charged bacterial cell wall (Cohen and Poverenov 2022; Darvishi et al. 2022). Quaternary ammonium salts are most commonly used in tissue engineering, drug and gene delivery, and wound care (Jung et al. 2020). Incorporating permanent quaternary ammonium groups gives chitosan a stable, pH-independent positive charge, greatly enhancing its solubility in water and allowing it to function effectively at neutral pH. Thus, these derivatives enhance the release and penetration of drugs through biological barriers in neutral or alkaline environments. In particular, these derivatives possess a permanent positive charge, enhanced mucoadhesiveness, and a high drug loading capacity, in addition to being biocompatible, non-toxic, and biodegradable. For these reasons, they are optimal candidates for the development of conventional and innovative drug delivery systems through various routes of administration, including oral, nasal, buccal, ocular, pulmonary, topical, and other mucosal delivery pathways (Fabiano et al. 2020). N-2-hydroxypropyl trimethyl ammonium chloride chitosan (N-2-HACC) is a type of positively charged quaternized chitosan that is more soluble in water than chitosan. N-2-HACC shows significantly improved antibacterial activity due to the introduction of quaternary phosphonium salt. A previous study showed that N-2-HACC has very low toxicity and high safety levels. A study conducted by Gao et al. showed that the water solubility of N-2-HACC is best at an 80% level of substitution (Gao et al. 2024). Wang et al. investigated the ability of N-2-HACC to transform from a sol to a gel under specific thermal conditions by preparing thermosensitive hydrogels based on N-2-HACC and glycerophosphate-containing liposomes loaded with doxorubicin. *In vivo* tests on rats showed significant inhibition of tumor growth but also several side effects, including significant weight loss. Side effects can be reduced by encapsulating the drug in liposomes; however, this, in turn, leads to a reduction in anticancer activity (Wang et al. 2013).

While quaternization confers a permanent positive charge that enhances solubility, mucoadhesion, and antimicrobial activity, alternative modification strategies aim to introduce carboxyl groups that impart amphoteric behavior, pH responsiveness, and distinct physicochemical profiles.

Carboxylated chitosan

Another well-studied chemical modification of chitosan is its carboxylation. The carboxylation reaction affects only the hydroxyl or amino group of the chitosan molecule or both active groups simultaneously. The water solubility, biocompatibility, and antibacterial properties of chitosan can be significantly improved by introducing carboxyl groups. In addition, carboxylated chitosan,

which has better flocculation, thickening, and film-forming properties than chitosan, is widely used in medicine, agriculture, and other fields. Currently, carboxymethyl chitosan (CMC) is one of the most widely used derivatives of chitosan. CMC exists in three different derivatives, namely N,O-carboxymethyl chitosan (N,O-CMC), O-carboxymethyl chitosan (O-CMC), and N-carboxymethyl chitosan (N-CMC). In chitosan, carboxymethyl groups are most commonly introduced at C6–OH, followed by C2–NH₂ and C3–OH, but the substitution sites can be directed through appropriate selection of reaction conditions and reagents (Chen et al. 2022). Doshi et al. prepared O-CMC by reacting chitosan with 10% sodium hydroxide in isopropanol at 50 °C to form a C6–O anion, followed by the addition of drops of monochloroacetic acid to obtain the desired product, which is then washed with ethanol, centrifuged, and dried overnight at room temperature. Under these conditions, a mixture of O-CMC and N,O-CMC is typically formed; however, O-CMC can be formed selectively by conducting the reaction in a cold bath or at room temperature (Doshi et al. 2018; Cohen and Poverenov 2022). Chaiwong et al. studied CMC of different molecular weights and found that all forms showed greatly improved water solubility, with viscosity increasing as molecular weight rose. Low-MW CMC displayed the strongest antioxidant activity, while high-MW CMC provided the best moisturizing effect, outperforming common moisturizers. These results indicate that high-MW CMC is suitable as a thickener and emulsion stabilizer, whereas low-MW CMC is better suited for antioxidant applications in cosmetics (Chaiwong et al. 2020).

Some of the main applications of O-CMC are presented in Fig. 3 (Bose and Sarkar 2020; Zhang et al. 2022).

O-CMC has demonstrated promising results as a drug delivery system for controlled release and targeted therapy due to its proven advantages – pH sensitivity, solubility, absorbency, non-toxic degradation products, controlled biodegradability, adhesion, ease of application, and sustained drug release (Chen et al. 2004). Another significant advantage of O-CMC is its compatibility with hydrophilic, hydrophobic, and amphiphilic drugs. Additionally, it can transport peptides, proteins, DNA, and genes and can be utilized in various forms, including films, nanoparticles, hydrogels, tablets, and microcapsules. Various drug models have been developed based on O-CMC containing doxorubicin or paclitaxel, which displayed improved antitumor activity and enhanced inhibition of tumor cell growth (Chen et al. 2024). Lu et al. investigated the possibility of alleviating inflammatory processes and associated pain using a conjugate of O-SMS with the water-insoluble ginsenoside Rh₂. In their study, the O-CMC–Rh₂ complex exhibited a more pronounced anti-inflammatory and analgesic effect than ginsenoside alone. In addition, O-CMC–Rh₂ is pH-dependent, which determines the rate of release of the anti-inflammatory agent. Under acidic conditions (pH 5.8), Rh₂ is released quickly, whereas at neutral pH, the release rate increases after 40 hours (Lu et al. 2023).

Figure 3. O-Carboxymethyl chitosan and its key applications in drug delivery platforms, wound healing materials, tissue-engineered constructs, and anti-cancer therapies (created with BioRender; accessed February 2025).

Carbohydrate-modified chitosans

Besides charge-based modifications such as carboxylation, chitosan can also be functionalized through covalent conjugation with carbohydrates, yielding derivatives with enhanced bioactivity and cell-interactive properties.

A method has been developed to create water-soluble chitosan derivatives with glucose using the Maillard reaction. The Maillard reaction has been known for over 100 years since French chemist Louis-Camille Maillard first reported the non-enzymatic reaction between reducing sugars and amino acids, peptides, or proteins in 1912 (Maillard 1912; Charnock et al. 2022). The rate of the Maillard reaction (MR) is influenced by multiple factors, including the nature and combination of reactants, their concentrations, initial pH, water activity, temperature, and reaction time. Of these parameters, the choice of reactants is crucial. For instance, the reaction proceeds more quickly with smaller reducing sugars; pentoses have been shown to react faster than hexoses (Yu et al. 2020). Maillard reaction products of chitosan consistently exhibit significantly enhanced antioxidant capacity – up to fivefold greater than neat chitosan – because the reaction introduces additional reactive functional groups and generates potent intermediate and final Maillard products, with higher reaction progression leading to stronger radical-trapping and electron-donating properties (Kraskouski et al. 2022). Chitosan derivatives linked to carbohydrates, such as D- and L-fructose, lactose, galactose, and mannose, exhibit a specific interaction with cells and demonstrate a high level of cell recognition ability. Cyclodextrin-linked chitosan derivatives have shown beneficial properties for application as a drug delivery matrix in cosmetics and analytical chemistry (Boeriu and van den Broek 2019). Fig. 4 shows the synthesis of a chitosan–glucose derivative obtained by Gullón et al. The influence of various reaction parameters, including temperature (40, 60, and 80 °C), glucose concentration (0.5%, 1%, and 2% w/v), and reaction time (72, 52, and 24 h), was investigat-

ed. The reaction progress was tracked by monitoring UV absorbance, browning, and fluorescence. Under optimal conditions – 2% (w/v) chitosan and 2% (w/v) glucose at 60 °C for 32 h – a chitosan–glucose (Chit–Glc) conjugate was isolated and structurally characterized to verify its formation (Gullón et al. 2016).

Chung et al. examined the Maillard reaction between α - and β -type chitosans – derived from shrimp and squid, respectively – and various saccharides to produce water-soluble chitosan derivatives. The α -type chitosan was available at 75% and 90% degrees of deacetylation (DD), while the β -type was supplied only at 90% DD. Reaction conditions such as temperature, pH, saccharide type and concentration, chitosan DD, and reaction time were systematically evaluated, as these parameters strongly influenced the yield and solubility of the resulting derivatives. Of the two types, α -chitosan produced higher-solubility derivatives and was therefore considered the more suitable substrate. Higher DD and the use of monosaccharides such as glucose, fructose, or glucosamine led to improved yields and solubility, whereas disaccharides like maltose decreased the yield due to excessive side reactions. Extended reaction times resulted in increased product complexity and crystallization during freeze-drying, reducing solubility (Chung et al. 2005). Chitosan–glucose derivatives exhibit significantly improved solubility at neutral or basic pH, in addition to a higher chelating capacity for metal ions and increased antibacterial and antioxidant activity compared to natural chitosan (Chuang et al. 2024). Another potential application of chitosan derivatives obtained through the Maillard reaction is as food supplements with an auxiliary anti-diabetic effect or for weight reduction purposes (Bandiwadkar et al. 2023).

Chitosan grafting polymerization

Carbohydrate conjugation is not the only strategy for chitosan modification; graft polymerization, also known as grafting, provides a complementary route for tuning its

Figure 4. Synthetic pathway for glycated chitosan based on the Maillard-type reaction between chitosan's primary amines and glucose (created with BioRender; accessed February 2025).

physicochemical properties. This is a process in which monomers are covalently bonded as side chains to the main polymer chain (backbone). The new polymers created in this way are also known as graft copolymers because they contain at least two different types of monomer units that are structurally different from the main chain (Sherazi 2014). This technique has the potential to improve the solubility, nanoscale morphology, and biocompatibility of the starting polymer. The physicochemical properties of a given polymer can be further modified by creating a copolymer with another polymer or by grafting (Purohit et al. 2023). Various chitosan graft polymers have been developed, such as chitosan-graft-poly(lactide) to chitosan: the grafting from and grafting onto techniques. In the grafting onto method, the pre-synthesized terminal functional chains of PLA are chemically bonded to chitosan through its amino or hydroxyl functional groups, while in the grafting from method, ring-opening polymerization of the lactide monomer is initiated from the functional groups of chitosan. The resulting derivatives exhibit excellent biocompatibility and low cytotoxicity, which have been confirmed by *in vitro* cytotoxicity assays (e.g., MTT, CCK-8, and Live/Dead staining), which consistently show high cell viability (>80–90%) across multiple cell lines, including fibroblasts, osteoblast-like cells, and endothelial cells. In addition, cell adhesion and proliferation studies demonstrate normal cell morphology and sustained growth on these materials, indicating the absence of toxic degradation products or adverse cellular responses. These qualities make chitosan–poly(lactide

graft polymers suitable materials for tissue engineering. Amphiphilic chitosan–poly-L-lactide copolymers have been investigated as promising drug delivery materials because their structure contains both hydrophilic (chitosan) and hydrophobic (poly-L-lactide) segments. This dual character enables them to self-assemble into nanoscale carriers capable of encapsulating a wide variety of therapeutic compounds, improving drug solubility, stability, and controlled release. Their biocompatibility and biodegradability further support their potential use as safe and effective drug carriers (Kaliva et al. 2020). In another study, poly(ortho-toluidine) was grafted onto chitosan (Cs-g-POT) using chemical and electrochemical polymerization methods. Cs-g-POT was characterized using FTIR, UV-Vis, and ^1H NMR spectroscopy techniques. The thermal behavior of the copolymer was investigated by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). Images of the copolymer surface obtained by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) confirm the successful attachment of POT to chitosan and demonstrate that graft polymerization was successfully performed by both methods. The resulting homogeneous Cs-g-POT copolymer simultaneously manifested suitable solubility in dilute acidic aqueous media and polar aprotic solvents (e.g., DMSO and N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone), with high physical stability and excellent processability properties. The graft polymers thus obtained showed good antibacterial activity against *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* by inhibiting bacterial growth, the highest activity being against *Escherichia coli* (Hosseini et al. 2024).

While graft polymerization enables extensive architectural modification of chitosan through polymeric side chains, a more targeted approach to amphiphilicity and self-assembly can be achieved by introducing hydrophobic substituents.

Hydrophobic chitosan modifications

The development of hydrophobic derivatives of polysaccharides has also attracted increasing interest. The hydrophobization of polysaccharides is widely used to alter their hydrophilic–lipophilic balance and, consequently, the rheological properties of their aqueous solutions. The lipophilic interaction of the introduced side substituents leads to the aggregation of macromolecules in an aqueous medium, resulting in the formation of nanoparticles with a core–shell structure, micelles, or gels, depending on the polymer concentration, temperature, and number and length of the alkyl substituent chains. Such chitosan derivatives are mainly employed for the development of amphiphilic carriers for drug delivery. Hydrophobization is usually achieved by introducing alkyl substituents of varying lengths into the chitosan structure through reactions of its amino groups with fatty acids or their anhydrides, producing acylated derivatives. A study was conducted on the mechanochemical alkylation reactions of chitosan when interacting with docosylglycidyl and hexadecylglycidyl ethers in the absence of solvents during shear deformation in a pilot twin-screw extruder. The chemical structure and physical properties of the obtained derivatives were characterized by elemental analysis, FTIR spectroscopy, dynamic light scattering, scanning electron microscopy, and mechanical tests. According to calculations for water-soluble products, it is possible to introduce approximately 5–12 hydrophobic fragments per chitosan macromolecule with a degree of polymerization of 500–2000. The length of the carbon chain of the alkyl substituent significantly affects its reactivity under the selected conditions of mechanochemical synthesis. It has been demonstrated that the modification disrupts the ability of macromolecules to form groups, resulting in an increase in plasticity and a decrease in the elastic modulus of films made from hydrophobically modified chitosan samples (Akopova et al. 2021). The dependence of the behavior of hydrophobically modified chitosan on the length of the substituent chains is clearly expressed in the synthesis of lauroyl chitosan. By introducing a lauroyl residue containing 12 carbon atoms, the newly obtained derivative has lower thermal stability than chitosan, which is attributed to weaker inter- and intramolecular hydrogen bonding. The thermal stability of chitosan derivatives increases with increasing degree of substitution due to the introduction of hydrophobic interactions. With an increase in the degree of substitution of modified chitosan derivatives from 5% to 15%, the onset of decomposition shows a shift to higher temperatures. Amphiphilic molecules typically self-assemble into micelles in aqueous environments, and this behavior in hydrophobically modified chitosan derivatives depends on factors such as the degree of substitution, hydrophobic

chain length, and overall amphiphilic balance. In the case of lauroyl-modified chitosan, the C12 acyl chain provides insufficient hydrophobicity to drive effective self-aggregation. Consequently, lauroyl chitosan lacks the amphiphilic strength required for stable micelle formation in water (Aljashaami and Aiedeh 2021). An interesting approach is the development of palmitoyl glycol chitosan, a hydrophobically modified glycol chitosan. This modification confers amphiphilic properties on the molecule due to the presence of both hydrophilic and hydrophobic groups. Palmitoyl glycol chitosan can be used to deliver both hydrophilic drugs, such as bleomycin, and hydrophobic drugs, such as griseofulvin (Ways et al. 2018).

Below is a comparison of the key characteristics of the above main classes of chitosan modifications, highlighting the differences in their functionality and application potential.

Comparative analysis

Chemical modifications of chitosan can significantly improve its physicochemical and biological characteristics. However, it should be noted that each class of chitosan derivatives has different advantages and disadvantages, which in turn determine their potential to act as drug delivery systems. The introduction of thiol residues into the chitosan structure leads to excellent mucoadhesive ability and increased epithelial permeability owing to the formation of disulfide bonds between the molecule and the mucus. This ability of thiolated chitosans makes them suitable for the delivery of various drugs through the mucous membranes. It is noteworthy, however, that their effectiveness largely depends on molecular weight, pH, and the stability of the thiolating agent. In contrast, sulfated chitosan derivatives interact extensively with proteins and viral components, making them a very good choice for antiviral and anticoagulant therapy. Their synthesis and biocompatibility are influenced by the location of sulfation, which makes their safety and reproducibility questionable. Phosphorylated chitosans, on the other hand, have significantly better solubility, chelating ability, and pH-dependent gelation. Studies have shown their potential for tissue regeneration and as vaccine carriers. Their application may be limited at high substitution levels. The advantages of quaternary ammonium chitosan derivatives stem mainly from the introduction of a permanent positive charge onto the molecule. This leads to increased solubility independent of pH, improved antimicrobial activity, and enhanced drug penetration. Excessively high levels of positive charge can lead to negative interactions with the cell membrane. Some of the most versatile derivatives are carboxylated chitosans. Due to their solubility and compatibility with a large number of drugs, they can be used for controlled release via various routes of administration. Carbohydrate-modified chitosan derivatives mainly improve solubility and exhibit increased antibacterial and antioxidant activity. In recent years, hydrophobic modifications and modifications by graft polymerization have gained growing interest, as they impart amphiphilic properties to chitosan, enabling its use

as a carrier for both hydrophilic and hydrophobic drugs. Yet, the relatively demanding requirements for their formulation remain problematic.

Overall, this comparison highlights the fact that no single chitosan modification is universally optimal; rather, each derivative represents a trade-off between solubility, bioactivity, stability, safety, and manufacturability. Rational selection of the modification strategy must therefore be guided by the intended route of administration, therapeutic targets, and regulatory constraints. This relationship is reviewed in detail in the following section, which highlights representative drug delivery systems based on modified chitosans across different administration routes.

Chitosan modifications as drug delivery systems

To better illustrate how individual chitosan derivatives align with the demands of specific administration routes, Table 1 summarizes the suitability of major modification types across ocular, buccal, oral, transdermal, wound-healing, and injectable delivery systems.

With this route-specific applicability in mind, the next section examines individual studies demonstrating how particular chitosan modifications influence drug delivery outcomes. One illustrative example is the comparison between thiolated and unmodified chitosan nanoparticles for the delivery of selegiline hydrochloride. In male Wistar rats, the thiolated formulation produced significantly greater locomotor activity and reduced oxidative stress than the unmodified chitosan nanoparticles, underscoring how thiol functionalization can enhance therapeutic efficacy by improving permeability and prolonging drug residence on mucosal surfaces (Singh et al. 2016; Bhavsar et al. 2017).

It is important to note that the performance of carboxylated chitosan is highly dependent on the delivery platform and the biological environment. For instance, Di

Colo et al. investigated the effect of carboxylated chitosan on the ocular penetration of ofloxacin. The tests showed that while carboxymethyl chitosan did not improve drug penetration, its increased viscosity and improved mucoadhesion prolonged ofloxacin retention on the corneal mucosa. Hence, solutions with lower concentrations of ofloxacin than previously known ensured higher drug bioavailability, allowing the development of ophthalmic solutions of ofloxacin with reduced frequency of application (Di Colo et al. 2004). In contrast, when carboxylated chitosan is employed as a surface modifier in mesoporous silica nanoparticles, as reported for doxorubicin delivery (Lohiya and Katti 2022), it contributes to tunable release kinetics and enhanced cytosolic transport. These findings indicate that carboxylated chitosan does not uniformly improve drug permeability but exhibits context-specific functionality – serving primarily as a mucoadhesive polymer in solution-based ocular systems while acting as a pH-responsive release regulator in nanoparticle systems.

Wang et al. synthesized a chitosan-graft-glycerol monooleate derivative of chitosan. This hydrophobic modification was used as a carrier for oral administration of enoxaparin. The model demonstrated significantly enhanced oral absorption of the drug substance, as well as improved mucoadhesion. Chitosan-graft-glycerol monooleate nanoparticles loaded with enoxaparin showed over 3.5 times better efficacy compared to the enoxaparin solution (Wang et al. 2014).

Siew et al. developed nanoparticles composed of quaternary ammonium palmitoyl chitosan, simultaneously loading hydrophilic drugs (ranitidine) and hydrophobic drugs (griseofulvin and cyclosporin A). As a result, they reported increased oral absorption and bioavailability of both hydrophilic and hydrophobic drugs due to increased dissolution rate and improved mucoadhesion (Siew et al. 2012).

Reported applications of chemically modified chitosan in drug delivery are presented in Table 2.

Table 1. Comparative overview of chitosan derivatives across delivery routes. The table summarizes which chemical modifications are most appropriate for ocular, buccal, oral, transdermal, wound-healing, and injectable systems, along with the underlying rationale for their selection.

Route of administration	Most suitable chitosan modifications	Key advantages	References
Ocular	Thiolated chitosan; chitosan-N-acetyl-L-cysteine	Strong mucoadhesion, prolonged precorneal retention, sustained release	(Javed et al. 2023); (Elsaid et al. 2016)
Buccal/oral mucosa	Thiolated chitosan (gels, proniosomes)	Improved mucoadhesion, longer residence time, enhanced permeation	(Vashist and Gadewar 2025)
Oral (systemic absorption)	Quaternized chitosan (TMC), N-trimethyl chitosan; Hydrophobic grafts (stearic acid, palmitoyl, glyceryl monooleate)	Tight-junction opening, pH-independent solubility, improved hydrophobic drug encapsulation, reduced P-gp efflux	(Yuan et al. 2012); (Ways et al. 2018); (Zariwala et al. 2018)
Transdermal (microneedle patches)	Thiolated chitosan	Enhanced mechanical strength, uniform microchannel formation, prolonged release	(Khalid et al. 2023)
Wound healing	Glycol chitosan hydrogels	Hydrophilic matrix, moisture retention, controlled antimicrobial release, activity against resistant strains	(Zhu et al. 2017)
Intravenous/injectable (nanoparticles)	Carboxymethyl chitosan; carboxylated chitosan	High aqueous solubility, predictable degradation, tunable release, improved cellular uptake	(Moghaddam et al. 2020); (Lohiya and Katti 2022)
Topical (non-ocular)	Hydrophilic or carboxylated chitosan derivatives	Film formation, local sustained delivery, low irritation potential	(Bose and Sarkar 2020); (Chen et al. 2024)

Table 2. Summary of studies using chemically modified chitosan for drug delivery.

Chemical modification of chitosan	Drug delivery system	Active substance	Application	Advantages	Limitations	References
Thiolated chitosan	Nanoparticles	Tobramycin	Topical ocular	Improved precorneal retention; sustained drug release; high ocular availability at low doses and dosing frequencies	Evidence mainly preclinical; long-term ocular safety and comparison with other mucoadhesive polymers insufficient	(Javed et al. 2023)
Thiolated chitosan	Microneedle patch	Dydrogesterone	Transdermal	Enhanced mechanical strength and microchannel uniformity; improved drug release and physicochemical stability	Advantages mostly formulation-based; lacks <i>in vivo</i> pharmacokinetic validation	(Khalid et al. 2023)
Thiolated chitosan	Mucoadhesive proniosomal gel	Curcumin	Buccal – for treatment of oral mucositis	Increased mucoadhesion time; sustained release and prolonged delivery of drugs through buccal delivery	Only <i>in vitro/ex vivo</i> data; no <i>in vivo</i> mucositis model confirmation	(Vashist and Gadewar 2025)
Glycol chitosan	Hydrogel	Colistin	Wound healing	Maintains antibacterial activity; active vs. colistin-resistant strains; biocompatible release in mice	Does not enhance potency over free drug; benefit mainly local delivery	(Zhu et al. 2017)
Carboxylated chitosan	Mesoporous silica nanoparticle	Doxorubicin	<i>In vitro</i> testing for breast cancer therapy	pH-responsive, tunable release; enhanced cytosolic delivery	Only <i>in vitro</i> ; lacks <i>in vivo</i> tumor efficacy/safety	(Lohiya and Katti 2022)
Stearic acid graft-chitosan	Micelles	Doxorubicin	Oral delivery	Good permeability; enhanced bioavailability of DOX reduced P-glycoprotein efflux	No <i>in vivo</i> oral pharmacokinetic data; unclear relative P-gp inhibition strength	(Yuan et al. 2012)
O-palmitoyl chitosan	Liposomes	Iron sulfate	Oral delivery	Increased liposomal iron encapsulation efficiency; significantly increased iron absorption in Caco-2 cells	Evidence limited to cell models; lacks <i>in vivo</i> systemic absorption confirmation	(Zariwala et al. 2018)
Chitosan-N-acetyl-L-cysteine	Nanoparticles	Ranibizumab	Topical ocular	Significantly improved ranibizumab loading; avoided initial burst release; favorable prolonged release profile	Stability/bioactivity of a biologic after release requires <i>in vivo</i> confirmation	(Elsaid et al. 2016)
N-trimethyl chitosan	Nanocomplexes composed of poly(lactic-co-glycolic acid) nanoparticles	Gemcitabine	Oral delivery	Tight-junction opening → increased permeability; 5-fold higher oral bioavailability; improved tumor inhibition	Increased permeability may raise toxicity risks; long-term GI safety unknown	(Chen et al. 2021)
Carboxymethyl chitosan	Nanoparticles	Paclitaxel	Intravenous	Increased cellular uptake and cytotoxicity	No biodistribution or <i>in vivo</i> efficacy data; lacks comparison to clinical PTX nanoformulations	(Moghaddam et al. 2020)

Overall, the studies summarized in Table 2 show that chemically modified chitosans offer diverse and highly context-dependent advantages. Thiolated and N-acetyl-L-cysteine-modified chitosans primarily enhance mucoadhesion and surface retention, making them effective for ocular and buccal systems, while hydrophobic grafts such as stearic acid, palmitoyl, and glyceryl monooleate significantly improve oral absorption by increasing permeability and facilitating drug encapsulation. In contrast, carboxylated derivatives mainly contribute to pH-responsive or tunable release rather than enhanced penetration. N-trimethyl chitosan stands out for its strong permeation-enhancing effect via tight-junction modulation, although its long-term safety remains insufficiently explored. Collectively, these findings highlight that each modification confers specific mechanistic benefits, and their effectiveness depends on matching the chemical

functionality to the intended route of administration and therapeutic goals.

Safety and regulatory aspects

Chitosan is considered biocompatible, biodegradable, and non-toxic, and these properties can be altered through various chemical modifications. Therefore, each new derivative has to undergo a safety assessment, as it cannot be assumed to be equivalent to pure chitosan. Thiolated and quaternary ammonium derivatives significantly improve mucoadhesion and permeability, but their long-term use may cause disruption of epithelial membrane integrity or tight junctions. The biodegradation of hydrophobic graft polymers and chitosan derivatives with high substitution levels may result in products whose long-term effects have

not yet been fully studied. In the same context, sulfated and phosphorylated chitosans, despite their potential to act as antiviral and anticoagulant agents, may interact strongly with plasma proteins, making their safety assessment highly dose-dependent.

From a regulatory standpoint, the status of chitosan remains complex. In the United States, where chitosan is generally recognized as safe (GRAS) only for specific food and dietary applications, its use in drug delivery systems is restricted (Kantak and Bharate 2022). Regulatory agencies such as the FDA and EMA have currently approved chitosan usage primarily as a biological material in a limited number of approved medical devices and wound dressings, while its derivatives are designated as novel substances requiring a comprehensive assessment in terms of degree of deacetylation, molecular weight, and batch consistency (Zia 2025). The numerous chemical modifications of chitosan are essential for transforming this natural polysaccharide into a biomaterial with various therapeutic applications. However, this diversity of options brings about novel chemical compounds whose biodistribution, biodegradation, and toxicological profiles have not yet been fully studied (Parchen et al. 2025). Importantly, there are no harmonized global guidelines for modified chitosans, which means that each derivative must undergo an individual quality and safety assessment. Therefore, the successful implementation of advanced chitosan-based drug delivery systems will depend on the development of standardized synthesis protocols, reliable toxicological data, and clear regulatory strategies tailored to the intended clinical application.

Challenges and future directions

In recent years, the application of chitosan and its derivatives has seen remarkable development. However, the development of new derivatives with various applications is a lengthy process, which slows their widespread distribution and industrial production. For this reason, in addition to improving chitosan modification techniques, it is necessary to increase interest in the practical application of these derivatives, especially in the field of biomedicine. Further studies on the graft polymerization of chitosan with long-chain groups, as well as its combination with antioxidant, antitumor, and antibacterial drugs, may result in the production of chitosan derivatives with improved characteristics, which in turn will expand their range of applications. These conditions require continuous improvement of preparation methods for chitosan itself and chitosan derivatives, as well as the investigation of more cost-effective production techniques to boost production capacities.

On the other hand, such an increase would entail difficulties for derivatives obtained through multi-step chemical reactions such as sulfation, phosphorylation, or hydrophobic graft polymerization. Future research should include advances *in vitro* models, along with long-term *in vivo* studies that clarify functional effica-

cy under clinically relevant conditions. Thus, promising laboratory results can be practically implemented in the development of drug delivery systems, while considerable attention is paid to safety, biodegradability, and regulatory approval.

Conclusion

Chemically modified chitosan has emerged as a highly promising biomaterial for drug delivery applications due to its improved solubility, enhanced mucoadhesiveness, and tunable physicochemical properties. Through chemical modifications such as carboxymethylation, quaternization, thiolation, hydrophobic grafting, and copolymerization, key limitations of native chitosan can be effectively addressed, enabling targeted, sustained, and stimuli-responsive drug release. However, as this review has highlighted, no single modification strategy is universally optimal; rather, each derivative presents a balance between solubility, bioactivity, stability, safety, and manufacturability that must be matched to the intended route of administration and therapeutic goals. As demonstrated by numerous *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies, modified chitosan derivatives exhibit favorable biocompatibility and can accommodate a broad range of therapeutic agents, including small molecules, peptides, proteins, and nucleic acids. Future progress will depend on a deeper understanding of structure–activity relationships, the development of scalable and reproducible synthesis methods, and clearer regulatory pathways, all of which are essential for translating advanced chitosan-based systems into clinically and industrially viable drug delivery platforms.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

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Author contributions

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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